

SYNTHESIS OF *p*-SUBSTITUTED α -BROMO- α -FORMYLACETOPHENONES

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Synthesis and characterisation of bromo-oxymethylene-*p*-(chloro, bromo, methoxy and methyl)-acetophenones have been described. They have been obtained both from sodium and copper salts of their respective oxymethylene-ketones. The copper complex method has afforded, in general, better yields of purer products.

Bromo-oxymethylene-acetophenone (α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone) (I, X=H) was prepared by Agarwal, Gupta and Deshapande (*this Journal*, 1949, 26, 55) by the bromination of sodium salt of oxymethylene-acetophenone in dry carbon tetrachloride. Another method for its preparation, furnishing a better and purer yield, has been recently described by Garg, Singh and Bokadia (*ibid.*, 1956, 33, 353). In the present communication synthesis of *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo-, *p*-methoxy- and *p*-methyl- α -bromoacetophenones have been described. These have been obtained by the bromination of sodium salts and also copper salts of their respective oxymethylene-ketones. Generally, sodium salt method gave gummy products, while the copper salt method afforded purer products.

The compounds were needed in connection with a synthetic work on heterocyclic compounds progressing in these laboratories.

The *p*-substituted bromo-oxymethylene-acetophenones are all colorless, crystalline compounds and respond to ferric chloride colour reaction; they form copper chelate compounds and liberate iodine with acidified potassium iodide solution (cf. Bokadia and Deshapande, *ibid.*, 1950, 27, 548; Bokadia, *Agra Univ. J. Res.*, 1953, II Sc., 9).

Copper complex of oxymethylene-*p*-aminoacetophenone has been synthesised and analysed. On bromination the copper complex gave a gummy product which could not be purified.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Chloro- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone.—A mixture of *p*-chloroacetophenone (Vogel, "Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green and Co., London, 1943, p 696) (7.8 g.) and ethyl formate (5 c.c.) was gradually added in small instalments with constant shaking to a well-cooled suspension of sodium dust (1.4 g.) in dry ether. The contents were kept

at room temperature for two days with occasional shaking to complete the reaction. The sodium salt was filtered at the pump, washed with dry ether and dried. The sodium salt was suspended in CCl_4 and bromine (8 g.), dissolved in the same solvent, was added gradually to the suspension kept at ice temperature. The sodium bromide was filtered off and from the filtrate the solvent was removed on a water-bath. A thick syrup was left which gave a gummy mass (6.5 g.), pale yellow in colour, m.p. 90° . Crystallisation from dry benzene furnished a colorless product, m.p. 108° . (Found: C, 42.2; H, 2.71; Cl + Br, 43.2. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{ClBr}$ requires C, 41.3; H, 2.3; Cl + Br, 44.1%).

In the other experiment the purified sodium salt was added to an excess of a saturated solution of copper acetate and the mixture was well shaken. The copper chelate compound was filtered, washed well with water and dried. The crude copper salt (m.p. 224° , 5 g.) was treated with bromine (4.9 g.) in the same manner as the sodium salt. The filtrate afforded a crystalline product (3.5 g., m.p. 102°) on evaporation and the pure product obtained on crystallisation, melted at 108° .

The bromo compound is insoluble in water but dissolves in dry benzene and absolute alcohol. It gives a violet colour with EtOH-FeCl_3 . It forms copper chelate compound with copper acetate solution, melting above 275° , after purification. (Found: Cu, 10.24. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{Br}_2\text{Cu}$ requires Cu, 10.86%).

On warming with acidified potassium iodide solution 1 g. mol. of the compound liberated 0.99 mol. of iodine.

p-Bromo- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone.—*p*-Bromoacetophenone (9.1 g.), obtained in the same manner as in case of *p*-chloroacetophenone (Vogel, *loc. cit.*) was formylated in the usual manner. The sodium salt was treated with bromine (8 g.). The filtrate on evaporation afforded a pale yellow gummy substance, crystallising from dry benzene in colorless solid, m.p. 114° , yield 6.8 g. (Found: C, 36.1; H, 2.1; Br, 52.6. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2$ requires C, 35.3; H, 1.99; Br, 52.2%).

The greenish blue copper complex of hydroxymethylene-*p*-bromoacetophenone (m.p. 260° , 6.5 g.) was treated with bromine (4.2 g.). The filtrate gave (3.0 g.) a solid product (m.p. at 98°) which after crystallisation melted at 114° .

The bromo compound is insoluble in water but dissolves in dry benzene and absolute alcohol. It develops a violet colour with EtOH-FeCl_3 . It formed copper chelate compound, m.p. 204° . (Found: Cu, 9.2. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cu}$ requires Cu, 9.45%). On warming with acidified potassium iodide solution, 1 g. mol. of the compound liberated 0.99 mol. of iodine.

p-Methoxy- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone.—The sodium salt of oxymethylene-*p*-methoxyacetophenone (7.8 g.) was treated with bromine (8 g.). The filtrate after recovering the solvent gave a syrupy liquid which on extraction with benzene furnished a pale yellow solid, m.p. 104° . On further crystallisation with benzene it melted at 109° , yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 45.9; H, 3.95; Br, 31.8. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{Br}$ requires C, 46.6; H, 3.5; Br, 31.1%).

The greenish blue copper chelate salt of oxymethylene-*p*-methoxyacetophenone melted at 199° after recrystallisation from chloroform. (Found: Cu, 14.2. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6\text{Cu}$ requires Cu, 15.2.). On bromination it gave a crystalline solid product, m.p. 109° , yield 1.6 g.

The bromo compound is insoluble in water but dissolves in dry benzene and absolute alcohol. It gives a violet colour with ferric chloride. It formed a pale green copper chelate which crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 168°. (Found : Cu, 10.9. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6Br_2Cu$ requires Cu, 11.03%). On warming with acidified KI solution, 1 g. mol. of the compound liberated 0.98 mol. of iodine.

p-Methyl- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone.—*p*-Methylacetophenone (Vogel, *loc. cit.*) was formylated in the usual manner. The sodium salt (8 g.) was treated with bromine (8 g.) at ice temperature. The filtrate on evaporation gave a pale yellow solid (m.p. 103°) which after crystallisation from dry benzene melted at 106°. (Found : Br, 34.3. $C_{10}H_9O_2Br$ requires Br, 33.1%).

On warming with acidified KI solution 1 g. mol. of the compound liberated 0.98 mol. of iodine.

Copper Chelate Compound of Oxymethylene-p-aminoacetophenone.—The sodium salt of the oxymethylene compound (7 g.) was dissolved in water and treated with copper acetate solution when a greenish blue copper chelate salt separated, m.p. above 255° (decomp.), yield 6 g. (Found : Cu, 15.6. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_2Cu$ requires Cu, 16.38%).

The above copper complex (3 g.) was suspended in dry CCl_4 and to it bromine (1 mol.), dissolved in the same solvent, was added gradually. The filtrate on evaporation gave a gummy mass which could not be identified.

The authors' thanks are due to Dr. O. N. Perti, Professor and Head of the Chemistry Department, for his interest in the work.

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Received July 11, 1956.